

Membrane potential based assay for SLC23A1 using HEK-293 SLC23A1 OE cells

PubChem ID: 1794810

Authors	Sara Tremolada ¹ , Loredana Redaelli ¹ , Lia Scarabottolo ¹
Affiliations	¹ Axxam S.p.A, Openzone Science Park, Bresso, Milan, Italy

Assay description

FLIPR[®] membrane potential dye measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, upon activation of SLC23A1. The assay allows the detection of ion channel and transporter modulation by increasing or decreasing the fluorescent signal as cellular membrane potential changes. When cells are depolarized dye enters the cells, causing an increase in fluorescent signal, conversely, cells hyperpolarization results in dye exit and decreased fluorescence (Figure 1).

SLC23A1 is crucial for the uptake of vitamin C (ascorbic acid) in most cell types, it is very selective for L-ascorbic acid; it couples the inward movement of this substrate against its concentration gradient to the simultaneous movement of sodium down its electrochemical gradient.

It is an electrogenic transporter eligible to be studied using the membrane potential dye.

Figure 1. Principal of a FLIPR[®] membrane potential dye assay. The assay measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, consequence of channels and transporters modulation. The fluorescent signal increases in intensity during membrane depolarization as dye follows the positively charged ions inside the cell. During membrane hyperpolarization, fluorescent signal decreases in intensity as dye follows the positively charged ions out of the cell.

Assay protocol

HEK-293 JumpIN-SLC23A1 cells were subjected to pharmacological characterization.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 80-90% confluent flasks and seeded at 10'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in medium without the selective antibiotics and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂. At the same time of seeding cells were induced with 1 µg/mL Doxycycline (not induced and mock control in parallel).

Membrane Potential assay

Medium was removed and cells were incubated 30 minutes at RT in 20 µL/well of FMP-Blue-Dye (0.5X dye dissolved in Standard Tyrode's Buffer as indicated in the manufacturer manual) and plates analysed at FLIPR^{TETRA} reader using a λ_{exc} 510 - 545nm / λ_{em} 565 - 625 nm filter.

Phloretin inhibitor was tested at a concentration of 300 µM directly dissolved in the FMP-Blue-Dye solution and incubated therefore for 30 min at RT.

To test pharmacology 20 µL/well of L-Ascorbic acid DR (2X in Standard Tyrode's Buffer), starting from 2 mM, 1:5 dilution steps (8 concentrations, only buffer included) was online injected at the plate reader and fluorescence recorded.

Data analysis

FLIPR^{TETRA} measurements obtained from different well replicates were analysed by using the Screenworks software (Molecular Devices, Version 3.0.1.4). Absolute Response (RFU) is obtained applying "Subtract Bias on Sample: n" (where n = Timepoint of compound injection) whereas Assay Window Response ($\Delta F/F_0$) is obtained applying "Response over Baseline" correction (where Baseline = Timepoint -1 and -2 before activator injection) and "Background Subtraction". Data were then exported as Area Under the Curve (AUC). Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create sigmoidal dose-response curves (variable slope) and to calculate EC₅₀/IC₅₀ values with GraphPad PRISM software (Version 6).

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC23A1
Synonyms	Na(+)/L-Ascorbic Acid Transporter 1, SVCT1
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 23 (Ascorbic Acid Transporter)
UniProt ID	Q9UHI7
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE028R-T (HEK-SLC23A1-WTOE-p5-6)

Assay data

<p>The figure contains three plots. The top plot is a dose-response curve showing AUC (Area Under Curve) on the y-axis (ranging from -5x10⁵ to 1.5x10⁶) versus log [L-Ascorbic Acid, M] on the x-axis (ranging from -8 to -2). It compares SLC23A1 not treated (orange squares), SLC23A1 doxy-treated (red squares), WT not treated (green triangles), and WT doxy-treated (cyan circles). The EC₅₀ for the doxy-treated SLC23A1 is indicated as 156 μM. The middle plot shows time-course AUC (0 to 5000) for SLC23A1 doxy-treated L-AA DR with various concentrations of L-AA (2 mM, 400 μM, 80 μM, 16 μM, 3.2 μM, 0.64 μM) and a buffer only control. The bottom plot shows time-course AUC (0 to 5000) for SLC23A1 doxy-treated L-AA DR in the presence of 300 μM Phloretin, showing a significant reduction in the response compared to the middle plot.</p>	Compound name (1)	L-Ascorbic acid
	PubChem CID	54670067
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma Aldrich, # A5960
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC ₅₀ , PoC, etc)	EC ₅₀ = 156 μM
	Compound name (2)	Phloretin
	PubChem CID	4788
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma Aldrich, # P7912
	Mode of action	Inhibitor
	Standard value type (i.e EC ₅₀ , PoC, etc)	IC ₅₀ = na Only one concentration of the compound was tested, showing an almost complete inhibition of the SLC. An inhibitor D/R is needed to calculate the IC ₅₀ .

Discussion

The Membrane Potential Assay for SLC23A1 showed a strong, specific and dose-dependent fluorescent signal upon injection of increasing doses of L-Ascorbic acid. Pretreatment with 300 μM Phloretin completely abolished cell depolarization effect upon L-Ascorbic acid injection.

<http://re-solute.eu>

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).